

INFLUENCE OF SPATIAL PARTICLE DISPERSION ON INCLUSION STRESS AND OVERALL STRAIN OF PARTICLE REINFORCED COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY: A full 3D stress analysis method based on the theory of eigenstrains and Eshelby's equivalency principle is proposed. The major difference between the proposed method and the traditional Eshelby solution is that the multiple inclusion interaction problem is solved, and thus the eigenstrains in each inclusion are not uniform. The multiple inclusion problem is solved by formulating a set of coupled singular integral equations in the unknown eigenstrains in each inclusion. The set of coupled singular integral equations are rewritten using a 26 point Gauss quadrature, which leads to a set of algebraic equations in the unknown eigenstrains. The obtained stresses from the stress analysis method are seen to be highly influenced by interparticle distance. Furthermore, based on the calculated volume averaged eigenstrains, a composite with regular dispersion of particles seems to have the largest effective stiffness of the dispersions considered in this study.

KEYWORDS: Particles, Eshelby's equivalent eigenstrains, singular integral equations, stress fields, effective quantities.

INTRODUCTION

Interaction between various types of heterogeneities such as cracks, flaws, reinforcing fibres or particles has been the subject of research for some years and various methods have been proposed. Crack-inclusion interaction effects on the local fields was investigated in [1-3]. The influence of cracks on the effective elastic properties were studied by [4-7]. The effects of inclusion shape and random inclusion dispersion on the effective properties have been the subject of intensive study and a vast amount of literature covers this subject, see e.g. [8,9] for references. Other morphological factors such as non-random particle dispersions, particle orientation, non-dilute volume fractions and imperfect fibre matrix interfaces have attracted increasing attention in the recent years. The effects of particle dispersion, particle orientation and imperfect fibre-matrix interfaces of heterogeneous materials were considered by [10-14].

Especially, the determination of local or effective properties of composites with non-dilute volume fractions calls for solutions which describes interaction adequately. Since no closed form solution of the governing equations exist for more than one inclusion, at least not for 3D problems, approximations of some kind are needed. Considering only the volume averaged eigenstrains [15,16], expanding the integrals as series [17,18] or dispersing the inclusions in periodic clusters, [19], enables the solution of the problem.

The present paper solves the system of coupled singular integral equations using a 26 point Gauss integration. The only limitation in the present theory is that the inclusions need to be spherical in order to use the 26 point Gauss integration. This means that the composite may be hybrid, i.e. contain different types of inclusions such as pores and/or particles of different stiffness. Furthermore, no assumptions regarding the inclusion dispersion is needed, thus the present theory can be used to

quantitatively and qualitatively evaluate various statistical dispersions in terms of e.g. extreme values of stress or overall stiffness.

The advantage of the present method is that once the eigenstrains have been obtained it is possible to calculate both local stress/strain fields and obtain informations on the overall effective properties of the considered composite.

In the paper a boldface italic capital letter denotes a fourth order tensor, $\mathbf{A} \equiv A_{ijkl}$ and the inner product of two fourth order tensors are denoted as $\mathbf{AB} \equiv A_{ijkl} B_{klmn}$ and analogous for $\mathbf{A}\boldsymbol{\varepsilon} \equiv A_{ijkl}\varepsilon_{kl}$. The inverse of a tensor is denoted as \mathbf{A}^{-1} . Second order tensors are denoted by boldface lowercase greek letters and vectors are denoted as ordinary boldface lowercase letters.

GOVERNING EQUATIONS

The governing equations for the multi inclusion problem is in the present paper based on Eshelby's equivalency principle. For inclusion I , the equivalency condition is

$$\mathbf{C}^I(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^\infty + \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^I) = \mathbf{C}(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^\infty + \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^I - \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^{I*}) \quad (1)$$

where \mathbf{C}^I and \mathbf{C} are the stiffness tensor of the inclusions and the matrix, respectively. $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^\infty$ is the applied strain, $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^I$ is the induced strain field due to the presence of inclusion I and $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^{I*}$ is the equivalent eigenstrain in inclusion I . The induced strain field, $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^I$, can be obtained as the sum of the induced strain field from the inclusion itself and the contributions from all the other inclusions present in the representative volume element as

$$\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^I(\mathbf{x}) = \int_{V^I} \mathbf{K}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}') \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^{I*}(\mathbf{x}') d\mathbf{x}' + \sum_{R \neq I} \int_{V^R} \mathbf{K}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}') \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^{R*}(\mathbf{x}') d\mathbf{x}' \quad (2)$$

where V^I and V^R are the volumes of inclusions I and R , respectively. N is the number of inclusions present in the the representative volume element and $d\mathbf{x}'$ is an infinitesimal volume centered at \mathbf{x}' . The kernel $\mathbf{K}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}')$ in Eq. (2) is given in terms of Green's function $G_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}')$ as

$$2K_{ijkl}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}') = -C_{pqkl} [G_{ip,qj}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}') + G_{jp,qi}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}')] \quad (3)$$

and $G_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}')$ is given as

$$G_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}') = \frac{1}{16\pi\mu(1-\nu)} \left[\frac{(3-4\nu)\delta_{ij}}{|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}'|} + \frac{(x_i - x_i')(x_j - x_j')}{|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}'|^3} \right] \quad (4)$$

and μ and ν are the shear modulus and Poisson's ratio of the matrix material, respectively. The first integral in Eq. (2) was shown by Eshelby to be constant when \mathbf{x} and \mathbf{x}' belong to the same inclusion. This constant is known as the Eshelby tensor and is denoted as \mathbf{S} . The above four tensor equations form a system of $6N$ by $6N$ coupled singular integral equation in the unknown eigenstrains. In order to solve these equations the singularity, occurring when $\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{x}'$, must be removed. This is simply done by rewriting the first integral of Eq. (2) as

$$\int_{V^I} \mathbf{K}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}') \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^{I*}(\mathbf{x}') d\mathbf{x}' = \int_{V^I} \mathbf{K}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}') (\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^{I*}(\mathbf{x}') - \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^{I*}(\mathbf{x})) d\mathbf{x}' + \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^{I*}(\mathbf{x}) \int_{V^I} \mathbf{K}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}') d\mathbf{x}' \quad (5)$$

now the first integral on the right hand side of Eq. (5) become zero, instead of singular, when $\mathbf{x}=\mathbf{x}'$ and the second integral equals the Eshelby tensor.

Since the 26 point Gauss integration is a surface integration the integrals in Eq. (2) are rewritten using Gauss' integral theorem. Once this is done the 6N by 6N coupled integral equations are decoupled and gives a set of (6 x 26 x N) by (6 x 26 x N) algebraic equations in the unknown eigenstrains.

Once the equivalent eigenstrains are found, the stress field in the matrix material is obtained as

$$\sigma_{ij}(\mathbf{x}) = \sum_{l=1}^N \int_{S^l} C_{ijkl} G_{km,l}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}') t_m(\mathbf{x}') dS^l \quad (6)$$

where the surface traction t_m is given in terms of the equivalent eigenstrains as

$$t_m(\mathbf{x}') = -C_{mnr s} \varepsilon_{rs}^*(\mathbf{x}') n_n$$

and the total stress field is obtained as $\sigma_{ij}^{\infty} + \sigma_{ij}(\mathbf{x})$.

NUMERICAL PROCEDURE

To obtain the algebraic equations a 26 point Gauss integration is carried out as, [20]

$$\frac{1}{4\pi a^2} \iint f(x,y,z) dS = \sum_{i=1}^{26} w_i f(x_i, y_i, z_i) + R \quad (7)$$

where R is of the order $O(a^8)$, a is the inclusion radius and the weight factors, w_i , and integration points are given in the table below

Points	Position (x,y,z)	Weight, w
1-8	$\left(\pm \sqrt{\frac{1}{3}}, \pm \sqrt{\frac{1}{3}}, \pm \sqrt{\frac{1}{3}} \right) a$	$\frac{27}{840}$
9-12	$\left(\pm \sqrt{\frac{1}{2}}, \pm \sqrt{\frac{1}{2}}, 0 \right) a$	$\frac{32}{840}$
13-16	$\left(\pm \sqrt{\frac{1}{2}}, 0, \pm \sqrt{\frac{1}{2}} \right) a$	$\frac{32}{840}$
17-20	$\left(0, \pm \sqrt{\frac{1}{2}}, \pm \sqrt{\frac{1}{2}} \right) a$	$\frac{32}{840}$
21-22	$(\pm a, 0, 0)$	$\frac{40}{840}$
23-24	$(0, \pm a, 0)$	$\frac{40}{840}$
25-26	$(0, 0, \pm a)$	$\frac{40}{840}$

Table 1: Gauss points and weight factors

Using this Gauss integration the induced strain field, $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^I$, is now expressed as

$$\begin{aligned} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^I(\mathbf{x}_i^I) &= 4\pi a^2 \sum_{j=1}^{26} w_j \mathbf{K}(\mathbf{x}_i^I, \mathbf{x}_j^I) (\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^{*I}(\mathbf{x}_j^I) - \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^{*I}(\mathbf{x}_i^I)) + \mathbf{S}^I \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^{*I}(\mathbf{x}_i^I) \\ &+ 4\pi a^2 \sum_{R \neq I}^N \sum_{j=1}^{26} w_j \mathbf{K}(\mathbf{x}_i^I, \mathbf{x}_j^R) \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^{*R}(\mathbf{x}_j^R) \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

This expression is inserted into the equivalency condition, Eq. (1), where I and R is summed over all the inclusions and i and j are summed over the number of Gauss points. When the equivalency condition is expanded this gives the set of $(6 \times 26 \times N)$ linear algebraic equations in the $(6 \times 26 \times N)$ unknown eigenstrains. As can be seen from Eq. (8), the Eshelby tensor, \mathbf{S} , with superscript I denotes the Eshelby tensor for inclusion I which means that the inclusions do not need to be of similar shape.

SURFACE AND VOLUME AVERAGED EIGENSTRAINS

Since the eigenstrains are obtained only on the surface of the inclusions, a relation between the surface averaged eigenstrains and the volume averaged eigenstrains are sought in order to determine effective quantities.

The actual expression for the eigenstrains is not known. However, the eigenstrains can be expressed as $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{ij}^*(x_1, x_2, x_3)$. This may be rewritten in spherical coordinates as $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{ij}^*(\rho, \phi, \theta)$.

Now, let p , h and g be arbitrary functions of ρ^n , ϕ , θ , respectively. The volume average of $f(\rho^n, \phi, \theta) = p(\rho^n)h(\phi)g(\theta)$ over a spherical domain with radius a , is then

$$\langle f \rangle_V = \frac{1}{V} \int_0^a \int_0^\pi \int_0^{2\pi} p(\rho^n) h(\phi) g(\theta) \rho^2 \sin(\phi) d\rho d\phi d\theta \quad (9)$$

and the surface average of $f(\rho^n, \phi, \theta) = p(\rho^n)h(\phi)g(\theta)$ over the same spherical domain is

$$\langle f \rangle_S = \frac{1}{S} \int_0^\pi \int_0^{2\pi} p(\rho^n) h(\phi) g(\theta) \rho^2 \sin(\phi) d\phi d\theta \quad (10)$$

the ratio between the volume averaged and the surface averaged quantities is now obtained as

$$\frac{\langle f \rangle_V}{\langle f \rangle_S} = \frac{n}{n+3} \text{ for } n > -3 \quad (11)$$

and the proof is straightforward

$$\frac{\langle f \rangle_V}{\langle f \rangle_S} = \frac{\int_0^a \rho^n \rho^2 d\rho \left(\frac{1}{V} \right)}{a^n a^2 \left(\frac{1}{S} \right)} = \frac{\left(\frac{a^{n+3}}{n+3} \right)}{a^{n+2}} \left(\frac{S}{V} \right) = \frac{a}{n+3} \left(\frac{3}{a} \right) = \frac{3}{n+3} \quad (12)$$

The fact that the ratio between averages is limited to $n > -3$ imposes restrictions on the assumptions regarding the expressions for the eigenstrains. However, for negative values of n the eigenstrains will become infinite at the center of the inclusion and this is not physically reasonable. On the other hand n can not become arbitrarily large, since that will cause the eigenstrains to become incompatible. In general only uniform or linear eigenstrains will be compatible, [21]. This leads to the following assumption of the eigenstrain expressions, in cartesian coordinates

$$\varepsilon_{ij}^*(\mathbf{x}) = B_{ij} + B_{ijk} x_k \quad (13)$$

where B_{ij} and B_{ijk} are constants.

From Eqs. (9) and (10) it is seen that the angular dependent parts are of no importance in the ratio between the averaged quantities, thus only the function $p(\rho^n)$ needs consideration.

It is assumed that $p(\rho^n)$ is of the form of a polynomial in ρ , in spherical coordinates as

$$p(\rho^n) \approx \sum_{n=0}^1 A_n \rho^n \quad (14)$$

where A_n are constants. This gives the relation between averages as

$$\frac{\langle f \rangle_V}{\langle f \rangle_S} = \sum_{n=0}^1 \frac{3}{n+3} = \frac{7}{4} \quad (15)$$

MATERIALS AND PARTICLE DISPERSIONS

The materials chosen for the calculations are glass inclusions embedded in a polypropylene matrix. The Young's moduli for the inclusions and matrix are: $E_f = 73000$ MPa, $E_m = 1500$ MPa, respectively. The Poisson's ratios are: $\nu_f = 0.3$ and $\nu_m = 0.32$, for the inclusion and matrix, respectively. All the inclusions are glass and of equal radii, $a = 0.01$ mm. With this inclusion dimension the residual, R , in Eq. (7), become of the order 10^{-16} . Since the present paper aims to describe the potential of the stress analysis method and not on the statistical characterisation of inclusion dispersions, the inclusions are only dispersed in a plane, since it is easier to distinguish the differences between 2D distributions than 3D distributions just by looking at them. However, ongoing work focus on 3D dispersions which are both characterised statistically and investigated in terms of stress fields and overall quantities.

The inclusion dispersions are obtained by placing a number of points – corresponding to the inclusion centers – regularly in a plane. Each point's position is perturbed within a small circle, see Fig. 1.

Fig. 1: The perturbation procedure used to obtain the dispersions

The new position of the inclusion is found using a random number generator. This procedure is repeated for all inclusions. A predefined value corresponding to the circle radius determines the irregularity of the dispersion, i.e. a large radius gives a highly irregular dispersion. For some values of

circle radius additional iterations are necessary since the inclusions are not points but particles of finite size and overlapping is not allowed.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Stress variation due to inclusion dispersion

In the present analysis the particles are dispersed in a plane and 3 different dispersion configurations are considered as shown in Fig. 2 below

Fig. 2: The 3 particle dispersions used in the calculations.

A load equal to 1 MPa was applied in the x-direction to all the configurations.

In the calculations of the inclusion stresses 41 inclusions are considered in each configuration.

However, the boundary inclusions (unfilled circles in Fig. 2) are left out of the subsequent analysis in order to avoid boundary effects influencing the results.

To distinguish between the three dispersions the simple statistical parameter describing each configuration is taken to be interparticle distance (IPD). The top left configuration is denoted as configuration #1, the top right configuration is denoted as configuration #2 and the bottom configuration as configuration #3. The minimum, mean and maximum interparticle distances and areas for the 3 configurations are

Configuration	min. IPD [mm]	mean IPD [mm]	max. IPD [mm]	Area [mm ²]
# 1	0.027	0.043	0.065	0.0438
# 2	0.0205	0.0417	0.0619	0.0408
# 3	0.0353	0.04098	0.05	0.04

The thickness of the volume in which the inclusions are dispersed is taken to be twice the inclusion diameter, that is 0.04. The volume fractions in the 3 situations thus become, $c_2^{\#1} = 0.06$, $c_2^{\#2} = 0.064$ and $c_2^{\#3} = 0.0655$, respectively.

It is shown that minimum interparticle distance is highly influencing the maximum particle stress as seen in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3: Maximum particle stress.

From Fig. 3 it is obvious that for decreasing minimum IPD the maximum particle stress increases. Also the variation in maximum stress changes drastically from particle to particle. A direct comparison between configuration #2 and #3 shows that the composite with particles distributed according to configuration #3 - a uniform distribution of particles - is least sensitive to failure for the same applied load level.

2. Overall properties

The overall composite strain may be obtained in terms of applied strain and volume averaged eigenstrain as

$$\bar{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}} = \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^\infty + c_2 \langle \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^* \rangle \quad (16)$$

However, it is more informative to calculate the effective composite stiffness, since the overall strain may easily be obtained once the overall stiffness is determined.

The effective stiffness can be obtained via the 6 separate load cases, $\sigma_{ij}^\infty = 1$ MPa, which, when applied to the composite, enables the computation of the averaged inclusion stress, $\langle \boldsymbol{\sigma}^{(2)} \rangle$ in the 6 load cases. The calculated average inclusion stress is then inserted into

$$\mathbf{M}^{\text{eff}} \boldsymbol{\sigma}^\infty = \mathbf{M}^{(1)} \boldsymbol{\sigma}^\infty + c_2 \left(\mathbf{M}^{(2)} - \mathbf{M}^{(1)} \right) \langle \boldsymbol{\sigma}^{(2)} \rangle \quad (17)$$

where $\mathbf{M}^{(\text{eff})}$, $\mathbf{M}^{(1)}$, $\mathbf{M}^{(2)}$ are the effective compliance, the matrix material compliance and the fibre compliance, respectively. Since $\mathbf{C}^{\text{eff}} = [\mathbf{M}^{\text{eff}}]^{-1}$, the effective stiffness is readily obtained.

As shown previously the relation between surface and volume averaged eigenstrains is quite simple. However, in order to determine the effective stiffness the volume averaged inclusion stresses are needed so the relation between surface and volume averaged stresses need to be known. Based on the

assumption that the eigenstrains are given as Eq. (13) it turns out that the inclusion stress is also a linear polynomial, [21], thus Eq. (15) also holds true for the inclusion stresses.

Carrying out the calculations, for the composite with dispersion #1, gives the effective stiffness

$$C^{\text{eff}} = \begin{bmatrix} 2627.9 & 1154 & 1138.7 & 0 & 0 & 10.4 \\ 1154 & 2612.6 & 1141.3 & 0 & 0 & 2.5 \\ 1138.7 & 1141.3 & 2592.7 & 0 & 0 & -4.5 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 790.1 & 3 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 3 & 786.9 & 0 \\ 10.4 & 2.5 & -4.5 & 0 & 0 & 981.6 \end{bmatrix}$$

For the composite with dispersion #2, the effective stiffness is

$$C^{\text{eff}} = \begin{bmatrix} 2682.7 & 1173.7 & 1148.6 & 0 & 0 & 10.1 \\ 1173.7 & 2650.1 & 1147.7 & 0 & 0 & -17.6 \\ 1148.6 & 1147.7 & 2638 & 0 & 0 & 22.3 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 784.2 & -35.9 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -35.9 & 799.2 & 0 \\ 10.1 & -17.6 & 22.3 & 0 & 0 & 1002.1 \end{bmatrix}$$

and for the composite with dispersion #3 the stiffness is

$$C^{\text{eff}} = \begin{bmatrix} 2708.9 & 1178 & 1156.4 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 1178 & 2673.3 & 1152.9 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 1156.4 & 1152.9 & 2646.6 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 815.3 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 813.5 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1039.4 \end{bmatrix}$$

As can be seen from these results the irregularity introduces coupling effects between shear and normal components of stress and strain. Furthermore, comparing the stiffness matrix of dispersion #1 and #2, it seems that the with increasing irregularity the shear-normal coupling components of the stiffness matrix increase. Finally, the composite with the regular dispersion, (#3), has the largest stiffness and no coupling effects between shear and normal stress/strain.

As can be seen the last stiffness matrix it not orthotropic, which it should be. The reasons for this are believed to be due to the numerical integration of the inclusions stress and the assumption of the eigenstrain functions. Another assumption concerning the eigenstrain funtions and thus also on the inclusion stress just lead to another factor to be multiplied to the surface volume averaged inclusion stress and this will not alter the material symmetry of the stiffness tensor only change the component values. The deviation from orthotropy of the stiffness matrix is, however, less than 2%.

Another aspect which calls for attention is the coupling terms in the stiffness matrices for dispersions #1 and #2. At first hand these might be attributed to numerical inaccuracy. However, if this was the case small coupling terms would also be present in the stiffness matrix for dispersion #3, but the calculations of the coupling terms gives identically zero. Since the inclusions are dispersed in a plane

parallel to the x-y plane only one symmetry plane exist in the material. This means that the stiffness matrix should correspond to that of a monoclinic material, and that is indeed the case for dispersions #1 and #2, thus this indirectly verifies the model.

CONCLUSIONS

A full 3D stress analysis method based on the theory of eigenstrains have been developed. Using a numerical Gauss integration the set of coupled singular integral equations are solved. The used Gauss integration requires spherical inclusions, however, the theory itself is general and may be applied to materials containing inclusions with different stiffness, including zero stiffness. Since the main objective of the present analysis is to show the potential of the stress analysis method the inclusions are only dispersed in a plane.

The model captures the interaction effects through non-uniform eigenstrains in the inclusions.

A relation between surface averaged eigenstrains and volume averaged eigenstrains has been derived based on spherical domains. This relation is used to obtain the volume averaged inclusion stresses which are used for determining effective properties.

The maximum stress in 3 composites with different inclusions dispersions is seen to be highly influenced by minimum interparticle distance. This is reflected in the fact that the maximum stress increases drastically when the minimum interparticle distance is decreased.

It is seen from the fluctuations in maximum stress that a composite with a regularly dispersion of inclusions is least sensitive to failure compared to the other dispersions considered in this study.

Based on the volume averaged inclusion stresses the effective composite stiffness is calculated. For the irregular dispersions coupling between normal and shear stress and strain occur – corresponding to a monoclinic material. Furthermore, the interesting conclusion is that the composite with regularly dispersed inclusions has the largest overall stiffness and no coupling terms between shear and normal stress and strain occur in the stiffness matrix in this situation

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